

“CONSUMER SATISFACTION INDEX FOR MOBILE SERVICES OFFERED BY PRIVATE SERVICE PROVIDERS IN COIMBATORE CITY”.

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INTRODUCTION

The mobile industry is a subset of the telecommunications industry. Members of this industry include a number of multinational corporations with very wide reach, in addition to smaller companies. **According to Wisegeek72**, “Mobile telecommunication service is the service that carries out the process of sending, transmitting and receiving information over a distance with assistance of some sort of mobile phone.”

The main aim of this telecommunication sector is made up of companies that make communication possible on a global scale, whether it is through the phone or the Internet, through airwaves or cables, through wires or wirelessly. These companies are allow their subscribers to send the data in words, voice, audio, or video to be sent anywhere in the world. The telecommunications industry started in the 1830s, with the invention of the telegraph, the first mechanical communications device. The industrial service extended with each new invention: the telephone, radio, television, computer, mobile device. These technical advances changed how people live and to do the business.

At the earlier stage, telecommunication industries used physical wires connecting homes and businesses. In modern society, for the innovation of mobiles these industries change their trend to wireless digital technology is becoming the primary form of communication. Wireless communications are a very fast-growing sector within telecommunications. More and more communications and computing methods shift to mobile devices and cloud-based technology. This piece of the industry is the expected keystone for the continued global expansion of the telecommunications sector.

1. Wisegeek (2014),“What are Mobile Telecommunications?”, Available at <http://www.wisegeek.com/what-are-mobile-telecommunications.htm>

2. www.ibef.org

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

1. To know the demographic profile of the respondent.
2. To ascertain consumers’ satisfaction index regarding various services offered by telecom industries in study area.
3. To find out the problems faced by the consumers in using telecommunication services.

NEED FOR THE STUDY

India ranks as the world’s second largest market in terms of total internet users. The total number of internet subscribers increased to 757.61 million in January 2021. The total wireless or mobile telephone subscriber base increased to 1,163.41 million in January 2021, from 1,153.77 million in December 2020². As the market becomes more competitive, mobile telecommunication service providers are trying to maintain the market share.

For this purpose, they are focusing on retaining their existing consumers. In India, there is less research done on the topic like “consumer satisfaction regarding mobile telecommunication services” provided by telecom service providers. Therefore, the researcher decided to work out the research regarding consumer satisfaction index of mobile services offered by private service providers.

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

With the availability of new technologies, the variety and quality of services from telecom companies and internet service providers (ISP) are increasing, profit margins are decreasing, and the lines between telecom companies and technology vendors are hiding. This lead to the telecom industries to meet the competition among the telecommunication sector. Hence, they are forced to do the various forms of telecom services. It is very

important in the point of view of the telecom industry to have a study about the judgement and fulfilment of the consumers.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

- 1) The study area is limited to Coimbatore city.
- 2) The study is based on consumer satisfaction regarding telecommunication services.
- 3) The study concentrates the level of satisfaction of consumers about telecom services provided by selected telecommunication companies.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

Sources of Data

The validity of research depends on the systematic method of collecting the data and analyzing the same in the sequential order. The present study is based on primary data and is carried out in the Coimbatore City.

Sample Design

The data were collected from 192 customers using convenient sampling technique.

Area of the study:

Area of the study refers to Coimbatore city

Tools used

- Percentage Analysis

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

Every research study is to be set with certain limitations. Some of them are inherent in the research design, while some others become part of the study during various stages of research process. The present study is subject to the following limitations.

1. The present study is limited to certain areas of Telecommunication service providers only.
2. The sample groups have been restricted to Coimbatore district only.

3. The findings of the study may be generalized to Coimbatore district only.
4. The sample size restricted to 192 respondents.

Market share of telecom service provider

market share is a key indicator of **market** competitiveness, it enables executives to judge total **market** growth or decline, identify key trends in consumer behavior and see their **market** potential and **market** opportunity.

TABLE: 1

Market share of Telecom service provider

Sl. No	Service Provider	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Airtel	56	29.2
2.	Reliance Jio	82	42.7
3.	Vodafone Idea	31	16.1
4.	BSNL	15	7.8
5	Any other	8	4.2
	Total	192	100.0

Source: Primary Data

From the above data it is understood that Idea reliance Jio market is more than the others i.e. 42.7 percent are using by the consumers. Followed by the second largest market share i.e., 29.2 percent as per the consumer survey is Bharati Airtel. Next at the third place is Vodafone Idea service providers capture the market share of 16.1 percent. The last two lower market share is shared by BSNL 7.8 percent and other mobile service providers is 8 percent.

It is concluded that Reliance Jio Capture maximum of 42.7 percent market share.

Reasons for Using Mobile Phone instead of Land Line

Longevity of usage of this Subscriber

Cell phones are the perfect way to stay connected with others and provide the user with a sense of security and with the ever-increasing penetration of internet and social media, it become essential for any researcher or marketer to assess the longevity of services usage by the current and potential telecom users.

TABLE: 2

Longevity of usage

Sl. No	Service Provider	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	within one year	28	14.6
2.	1-3 years	49	25.5
3.	3-5 years	82	42.7
4.	above 5 years	33	17.2
	Total	192	100

From the above table it has been observed that, 42.7 percent of respondents’ are availing service from the same service provider for the past 3-5 years. Similarly, 25.5 percent of customers’ are using the service for the last 1-3 years and 17.2 percent of them use the same telecom company service above 5 years. Further it has been observed that 14.6 percent of sample populations’ avail mobile serve services for the last one year or less than that.

It is evident from the above data analysis that 42.7 percent of respondents’ are using mobile phone service providers for the past 3-5 years.

Factors influencing the selection of service

Mobile phones are used for a variety of purposes, such as keeping in touch with family members, for conducting business, and in order to have access to a telephone in the event of an emergency.

TABLE: 3

Reason for using mobile phone service

Sl. No	Service Provider	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	contact made easy	42	21.9
2.	speedy communication	51	26.6
3.	Mobility	31	16.1
4.	Prestige / Status Symbol	18	9.4
5	Cost economy	12	6.3
	Development of business	38	19.7
	Total	192	100.0

Source: Primary Data

From the above table it is revealed that 26.6 percent respondents selected the service for speedy communication, 21.9 percent of them are option for contact made easy. Followed 19.7 percent of them for development for their business, 16.1 percent of the sample population opting the service for their mobility. 9.4 percent using mobile services for showing their status or maintaining their prestige and finally 6.3 percent of them opted for cost economy.

It is concluded that maximum of the sample population (26.6%) opted the telecom service for the purpose of the speedy communication.

FINDINGS:

- Majority (53.2 %) of telecom service users are male.
- Majority (56.8%) of the telecom service users are the youth and middle aged retail Customers.
- Most (38.88%) of respondents' have pursued professional degree.
- Most (30.68%) of the respondents' are salaried employees working in various private organisations.
- Majority (69.79%) of sample populations' are married.

- Most (56.44%) of respondents' form a part of joint family.
- Most (30.68%) of the respondents' family constitutes of five members or more than that.
- Majority (51.29%) of respondents' family has two earning members.
- Majority (46.84%) of respondents' monthly income ranges between Rs.25001–Rs.35000.
- Most (42.7%)of the market share captured by Reliance Jio.
- 42.7 percent of respondents' are using mobile phone service providers for the past 3-5 years.
- most of the sample population (26.6%) opted the telecom service for the purpose of the speedy communication.

SUGGESTIOS:

- The service provider should improve the connectivity of the network.
- Make appropriate HRM policies. Personal relation of the employees with customers will improve customer satisfaction.
- Channels should be delivered with speed, accuracy, courtesy, and concern. Good service results when the provider meets or exceeds the expectations of the customers.
- Service providers should provide good enough and reliable services to their subscribers, for that they have to focus on the good quality services to their subscribers' time to time.
- Service providers should be more transparent in bill generation so that they earn the trust of the subscribers in case of post paid connections.

CONCLUSION:

The main purpose of the study is to know the consumer satisfaction index for the mobile telecommunication services offered by private service providers. From the elaborate

data discussion it has been inferred that, majority of the respondents' feel that availing the telecom service is convenient.

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